

Interaction of Cobalt(II) Schiff Base Complexes with Aromatic Nitro-Compounds

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Cobalt(II) salen and related compounds interact with aromatic nitro compounds showing a characteristic absorption band of high intensity in the region 420-432 nm. The energy of the transition has been found to have a reciprocal relationship with dielectric constant of nitrobenzene solution in alcohol, while obeying a direct relationship with a number of solvents including nitromethane. The energy of the absorption band for a series of aromatic nitro compounds is also related to Hammett's substitution constant signifying a major interaction probably of charge-transfer type due to coordination of the nitro group and minor interaction between the rings. A black nitrobenzene adduct with [Co(II) salen] has been isolated and identified. The role of the cobalt(III) in reduction reaction of substrates with reducing agent is suggested.

OXIDATION-REDUCTION reactions of cobalt complexes are comparable to the familiar red-ox systems like iron, copper and molybdenum both as regard to number and variety of reactions known. Such reactions are frequently encountered in catalysis^{1,2}, electron transfer³⁻⁷, reversible oxidation-reduction⁸⁻⁷ and biological processes^{6,7}. One particular aspect in which cobalt excels other transition metals is that it can exist in all the three possible thermodynamically and kinetically stable oxidation states—Co(III), Co(II) and Co(I). In contrast to the higher oxidation states, the stability of the Co(I) depends critically on ligand environment and geometry. On the other hand, Co(II) shows limited chemical activity compared with Co(I) and Co(III), the former being a highly reactive form in many catalytic reactions both *in vivo* and *in vitro* systems. The significance of Co(II) comes from a logical consequence of the formation of Co(I) from Co(III) via the Co(II) intermediate and the general belief is that Co(II) may play some minor yet useful part in the catalytic reduction of substrates with reducing agents in presence of Co(III) ion. Our interest in this particular direction come from the study of some reduction reactions of nitrobenzene catalysed by different cobalt complexes in presence of strong reducing agent like borohydride⁸. While trying with cobalt-salen complex we observed an interaction between Co(II) salen and organic nitro compounds, in particular, nitrobenzene. The present paper is a study in detail to explain this and to find a clue to the possible role of Co(II) ion in catalysis.

Experimental

[Co(II) salen] was prepared following standard methods^{9,10}. Since the Co(II) complex has a tendency to coordinate molecular oxygen in presence of bases, care was taken to eliminate such a possibility by removing impurities in the complex and solvents used. Elemental analysis, solution spectra and infrared spectra agreed with reported values. Deaeration with pure nitrogen gas was found to be the best way to get the Co(II) complex in solution which showed no change to the oxygenated complex or Co(III) complex for a sufficiently long time as evidenced from the spectra. The other cobalt complexes were prepared by known methods and solutions were made following the same deaeration procedure. Organic solvents were of analytical grade and were distilled prior to use. A Carl-Zeiss-PMQII spectrophotometer and matched 1 cm and 1 mm cells were used to record the spectra with an accuracy of ± 1 nm in wavelength. The pure solvent or an alcoholic solution with identical amount of solid compound were used as corresponding blanks. [Abbreviations, salen=bis-(salicylaldehyde) ethylenediimine, bae=bis(acyetylacetone) ethylenediimine, saloph=bis(salicylaldehyde) orthophenylenediimine, dmg=dimethylglyoxime.]

Results and Discussion

[Co(II) salen] is a red-brown complex in solid state. It gives a yellow-brown colour with ethanol.

With nitrobenzene it develops immediately a reddish brown colour. The high solubility of [Co(II) salen] in nitrobenzene compared with benzene, toluene, etc., and formation of a reddish colour suggest an interaction. In order to find out the cause of such change the effects of different organic solvents and nitro compounds on the solution spectra have been studied. The solvents have been chosen to see the effects due to aromatic ring at one end and nitro group at the other. Three other cobalt(II) complexes studied are [Co(II) bae], [Co(II) (dmg)₂] and [Co(II) saloph] with basically similar co-ordinating atoms and planar geometry. The spectra of [Co(II)salen] and related compounds have been studied in detail by a number of workers¹¹⁻¹⁴. In spite of the complex nature and possibility of solvation of the pseudo planar complex changing it to penta or hexacoordinate species, the various assignments have been made. In the solution spectra three main regions can be separated showing maximum absorptions in the form of peaks and shoulders. Below 320 nm there is one or more intense peak. The region around 500 nm appears as a shoulder of low intensity. In the intermediate region, which is of special interest to our problem, there are two distinct peaks in most non-aprotic solvents, the positions and intensity are very much dependent on the nature of the solvents. In alcohol like solvents a broad band is observed. In the ligand a high energy band around 320 nm has been characterised as $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and 390 nm band as $n-\pi^*$ transition. In the metal complex the 390 nm band disappears and the $\pi-\pi^*$ band moves to higher

wavelengths. The single band which we notice at 392 nm in ethanol is definitely this band. The splitting of the band in non-aprotic solvents may be due to an excitation interaction of the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the two azomethine groups¹⁴, but it appears the lower energy band of the two is related to the band with peak at 392 nm in ethanol. For our purpose we shall concentrate on this distinct band on the higher energy side of the shoulder which has a $\pi-\pi^*$ origin with the possibility of mixing of the π orbitals of the ligand and metal.

In Table 1 are given the spectral data of [Co(II)salen] in different solvents and in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 some typical spectra are shown. A freshly prepared solution of [Co(II)salen] in nitrobenzene

Fig. 1. Spectra of [Co(II) salen] (Conc. $10^{-4}M$) in different solvents: benzene (1), chloroform (2), toluene (3), ethanol (4).

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF [Co(II) SALEN] IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Dielectric Constant at 25°C ^a	λ_{max} in nm (ϵ_M)	
1. Ethanol	24.30	392(5420)	470(950) ^c
2. Methanol	32.63	390(3913)	450
3. Chloroform	4.81	354(7100)	410(7500) ^c
4. Benzene	2.28	355(6740)	417(7300)
5. Toluene	2.38	352(4900)	414(4380)
6. Xylene	2.37	298	370
7. Nitrobenzene	34.82	432(6700)	485(2540) ^c
8. o-nitrotoluene	27.40	434(7170)	480(3860)
9. m-nitrotoluene	23.80	430(7400)	485(3350)
10. p-nitrotoluene ^b	22.00	422	—
11. Chlorobenzene	5.60	416	500
12. Benzaldehyde	17.80	410	510 ^c
13. Acetophenone	17.39	386	445 ^c
14. Acetone	20.70	352	478(2300)
15. Dioxan	2.21	382(3350)	—
16. Nitromethane	36.00	390(4511)	450 ^c
17. Cyclohexanol	15.00	315	369
18. Cyclohexanone	18.30	368	445 ^c
19. Methylbenzoate	6.59	370	—
20. p-nitrophenol ^b	—	415	—
21. Acetonitrile	36.02	382(5240)	—

^a Dielectric constant values are quoted from Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, R. C. Weast and S. M. Salby, the Chemical Rubber Co., Cleveland Ohio, (1966) and U. Mayer, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, (1976), 21, 159.

^b Spectra in ethanol solution.

^c Absorption band appears as shoulders.

Fig. 2. Spectra of [Co(II) salen] (Conc. $10^{-4}M$) in nitrobenzene(A), *m*-nitrotoluene(B), *o*-nitrotoluene(C) and Cu(II) salen [Conc. $10^{-3}M$] in nitrobenzene(D).

shows an absorption maximum (λ_{max}) at 432 nm with a molar absorptivity (ϵ_M) of 6700, the corresponding values after 3 days are 430 nm and 4800. This signifies a great red-shift compared with spectra in ethanol (λ_{max} 392 nm, ϵ_M 5420). The spectra in nitromethane is very much similar to that in methanol and it appears that such a nitro group has very little effect on [Co(II)salen] spectra. Nitromethane may be thought to behave as methanol but for little influence due to solvent effects such as dielectric constant and solvation. In contrast, nitrobenzene and related aromatic nitro compounds have profound effect on the spectra resulting in large red shift. The energy of the band around 400 nm has been plotted against the dielectric constant of the solvents (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Energy plot of [Co(II) salen] absorption band around 400 nm against dielectric constant of solvents: benzene(1), toluene(2), chloroform(3), monochlorobenzene(4), acetophenone(5), benzaldehyde(6), acetone(7), ethanol(8), methanol(9), nitromethane(10), acetonitrile(11), nitrobenzene(12), dioxan(13), and I-VI nitrobenzene: ethanol mixtures in the proportion 90:10(I), 80:20(II), 60:40(III), 50:50(IV), 40:60(V), 10:90(VI).

Excepting nitrobenzene we observe a good linear relationship between energy and dielectric constant—energy increasing as the dielectric constant increases (Fig. 3, line AB). The energy of the band in nitrobenzene is much lower than expected from the

linear relationship. The peculiarity of the nitrobenzene from other non-nitro aromatic solvents like benzene, toluene and aliphatic nitro compound like nitromethane is thus apparent. Another aspect of the [Co(II)salen] spectra is the effect of mixed solvent of ethanol and nitrobenzene. In Table 2 are given the results for solutions with

TABLE 2—A. ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF [Co(II) SALEN] IN ETHANOL DILUTED WITH NITROBENZENE

Solvent		λ_{max} in nm
%nitrobenzene	%ethanol	
0.0	100.0	390
10.0	90.0	418
40.0	60.0	426
60.0	40.0	428

B. ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF [Co(II) SALEN] IN NITROBENZENE DILUTED WITH ETHANOL

Solvent		λ_{max} in nm
%nitrobenzene	%ethanol	
100.0	0.0	432
60.0	40.0	428
40.0	60.0	426
10.0	90.0	418

different percentages of nitrobenzene and ethanol. As the percentage of nitrobenzene increases the absorption maximum progressively moves to higher wavelength. A change in ϵ_M values observed depending on whether the original solution is made in one pure solvent and diluted with the other. As a typical case for a solvent composition of nitrobenzene and ethanol in the ratio 60:40 optical density at 428 nm for $10^{-4}M$ solution is 0.52 when the original solution is made in nitrobenzene and then diluted with ethanol, it is only 0.28 at the same wavelength when ethanolic solution is diluted with nitrobenzene. Such optical density measurements with complex solution in nitrobenzene are not however reproducible and consistent for meaningful scrutiny. In general, it seems that the interaction between nitrobenzene and [Co(II)salen] is a strong one and once this is achieved ethanol does not influence it much, at least initially. Also nitrobenzene does shift the equilibrium once it is set up between the complex and ethanol. The O. D. plot vs the percentage of nitrobenzene added to ethanolic solution at different wavelengths (Fig. 4) shows the increase in a similar way for solvent concentration in which 50% or above is nitrobenzene. The plot of energy of the absorption band vs dielectric constant of the mixtures taken as additive values shows again a linear relationship (Fig. 3, line CD) but here energy decreasing as the dielectric constant increases. Once again for the nitrobenzene system we notice a completely different picture directing our notice to the aromatic nitro group as the singlemost significant factor for the interaction. Generally we expect an inverse relation of energy with dielectric constant for bands of

Fig. 4. Plot of O. D. vs percentage of nitrobenzene added to ethanolic solution of the complex : O.D. at 410 nm(1), 420 nm(2), 430 nm(3), [Complex conc. $2 \times 10^{-4} M$].

charge-transfer origin. Probably what we notice in nitrobenzene [Co(II)salen] system have some charge-transfer features. Both nitrobenzene and nitrotoluene show red shifts with respect to benzene and toluene by an amount of 14 nm and 4 to 12 nm for different substituent positions. *m*-nitrotoluene is a better solvent than *p*-nitrotoluene for red shift. In all probability there are two effects, one is due to the coordination of the nitro group through oxygen atom to the metal ion and the second one is due to the interaction between the aromatic ring of nitrobenzene and ligand ring. The geometry of the complex is favourable for such interaction if nitrobenzene is coordinated through one oxygen atom of the nitro group. One way of looking at it is to observe the effect of different substituents on nitrobenzene as manifested in Hammett's substituent constant (σ). In Fig. 5, the energy of the band is plotted against Hammett's constant showing a reasonable linear relationship—an electron releasing tendency resulting in higher energy of transition. Although the effect is not very large it is quite significant because the dielectric constant acts in the opposite way. That *o*-nitrotoluene is similar to nitrobenzene means the electronic effect of the methyl group is off-set by the steric effect of the methyl group proximal to the nitro group. The oxygen donor solvents show also a linear relationship with D. C. (Fig. 3, line EF), similar to nitrobenzene and nitrobenzene-alcohol systems, indicating the same type of interaction of the cobalt complex with the solvent.

The interaction of the aromatic nitro compound with Co(II) ion seems to be a general phenomenon observed in the other systems like bae, saloph and dmg complexes of cobalt(II). Here we notice that

Fig. 5. Plot of transition energy (~420 nm band) against Hammett's substitution constant; nitrobenzene(1), *m*-nitrotoluene(2), *p*-nitrotoluene(3), *p*-nitrophenol(4).

with bae and dmg complexes the band appears at 430 nm close to the salen complex value, and for saloph complex it is at 442 nm. This enhanced effect can only be due to the presence of the additional ring in the ligand which interacts strongly with the aromatic system of the nitrobenzene both being planar and situated close enough to show-up this interaction, which is also present in similar delocalised systems. The relative shift have the order saloph (52 nm) > salen (42 nm), for dmg and bae they show the band in ethanol as broad shoulder. The final proof comes from the isolation of a nitrobenzene adduct from a concentrated solution of [Co(II)salen] in nitrobenzene left for a sufficient long time. The black solid adduct is unstable in alcoholic solution. The close resemblance between the i.r. data (Table 3) of the nitrobenzene adduct with the original complex suggest their basic structural similarities [the bands

TABLE 3—I.R. DATA OF THE COMPLEXES (IN KBr DISC) IN cm^{-1}

1. Co(II) salen					
685w,	728vs,	738w,	745vs,	765sh,	790m,
840sh,	845m,	900s,	920vw,	940sh,	950m,
970dw,	1020w,	1040w,	1048m,	1082m,	1122s,
1195s,	1148w,	1200ds,	1215sh,	1230vw,	1255vw,
1288s,	1325s,	1380w,	1428sh,	1450s,	1468s,
1528s,	1545w,	1565w,	1600s,	1625m,	1645-b,
2850w,	2940m,	3030-3090w,		3450bvs.	
2. Co(II) salen-nitrobenzene adduct					
655m,	715sh,	730s,	748vs,	792m,	840-850dm,
900vs,	975m,	and wt,	1025m,	1055m,	1082m,
1130s,	1330m,	1348s,	1385m,	1455vs,	1740s,
1540s,	1605s,	1635-1645 dvs,	2670w,	2800vw,	2860w,
2935m,	3030-3090bw,				3450bvs.
s=strong, sh=shoulder, m=medium, w=weak, v=very, b=broad, d=doublet, t=triplet.					

around 1450-1470 cm^{-1} are probably due to CH aliphatic bending and around 1545-1565 cm^{-1} are

for C=C (aromatic) stretch; band around 1645 cm^{-1} is responsible for C=N stretching, where as those around $2860\text{-}2935$ and $3030\text{-}3090\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to CH (aliphatic) and CH (aromatic) stretching respectively] excepting the appearance of strong bands at 1348 and 1540 cm^{-1} in the adduct. For nitrobenzene these two bands are at 1340 and 1530 cm^{-1} meaning a shift of $8\text{-}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the characteristic frequencies of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group, this can be due to the additional protection of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group from the adduct formation. Such adduct formation is known with chloroform for the $[\text{Co(II) salen}]^{15,16}$ and *p*-nitrophenol with $[\text{Cu(II) salen}]^{17}$. However, the attachment of the nitrobenzene is different from the attachment of the other two which forms adducts through hydrogen bonding with the oxygen atoms of the salicylaldehyde moiety of the ligand. Nitrobenzene also interact with $[\text{Cu(II) salen}]$ showing an absorption peak at 430 nm but with low intensity ($\epsilon_M 940$) [Fig. 2]. Very weak absorption ($\epsilon_M 45$) is also observed at the same wavelength region for salen in nitrobenzene. Thus Co(II) salen is by far the most interacting species. We can then make the following scheme for the interaction. One of the oxygen atoms of the nitro group is coordinated to the Co(II) ion at one axial position, being ideally situated for such coordination (Fig. 6). The N—O

Fig. 6

bond has some ionic character, so the Co—O bond is also conferred with some ionic character. Increase in electron density on the ring will reduce the same and will lead to a charge-transfer transition at higher energy. On the other hand, an electron withdrawing group will have the opposite effect. The aromatic ring of nitrobenzene remains coplanar with the $[\text{Co(II) salen}]$ system at close enough distance for interaction between the benzene ring parts of nitrobenzene and the ligand.

Since $[\text{Co(II) salen}]$ is capable of forming an associated complex with nitrobenzene (NB) it is possible to assign the role of Co(II) in the catalytic reduction of nitrobenzene with borohydride or similar reducing agents in presence of Co(III) salen complex⁸. Co(III) is initially reduced to Co(II) which probably activates the coordinated nitrobenzene in the associated complex. Further reduction of Co(II) to Co(I) results in two electron transfer to the nitrobenzene molecule, initially

activated, forming Co(III) and nitrobenzene reduction products. Another possibility is the direct reduction of nitrobenzene in the activated complex by the reducing agents involving one or more electron transfer coupled with protonation.

The above scheme may also be applicable to nitrosobenzene and other similar compounds.

References

1. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, *Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds*, Prentice-Hall, Inc. Englewood Clif, N. J. 1962, Chapter 8, p. 836.
2. A. E. BREARLEY, H. GOTT, H. A. O. HILL, M. O'RiORDAN, J. M. PRATT and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc., (A)*, 1971, 612.
3. A. BIGOTTO, G. COSTA, G. MESTRONI, G. PELLIZER, A. PUXEDDU, E. REISENHOFER, L. STEFANI and G. TAUZHER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.* 1970, 4, 41.
4. G. COSTA, A. PUXEDDU and G. TAUZHER, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1968, 4, 819.
5. G. N. SCHRAUZER, *Accounts Chem. Res.*, 1968, 1, 97.
6. H. A. O. HILL, *Inorganic Biochemistry*, Vol. 2, Ed. G. I. EICHORN, ELSEVIER, 1972, Chapter 90, "Corrinoids" p. 1067.
7. D. G. BROWN, *Progress in Inorganic Chemistry*, Vol. 18, Ed. S. J. LIPPARD, 1973, p. 177.
8. P. K. DAS and A. K. DE, communicated to *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*
9. R. H. BAILLES and M. CALVIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1886.
10. K. DRY, R. L. DE and K. C. ROY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 864.
11. B. BOSNICH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 627.
12. L. SACONI, M. CIAMPOLINI, F. MAGGIO and F. P. CARASINO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 3246.
13. G. E. BATLEY and D. P. GRADON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 877.
14. A. PASINI, M. GULLOTTI and R. UGO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1977, 346.
15. T. TSUMAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1938, 13, 247.
16. W. P. SCHARFFER and R. E. MARCH, *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. B.*, 1969, 25, 1676.
17. E. N. BAKER, D. HALL and T. N. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 400.